

The Effect of Organizational Support and Work Stress on Employee Performance with Satisfaction as a Mediating Variable

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ABSTRACT: The hospitality industry in Bali has great potential in line with the growth of new tourist destinations and changes in global tourism trends. This study aims to examine the theoretical and practical implications related to organizational support and employee performance in 3-star hotels in Badung, Bali. Data collection was conducted by distributing questionnaires to 110 employees of 3-star hotels in Badung Regency, Bali. Data analysis used inferential analysis using SEM PLS. Based on the results of the study, it was found that organizational support had a positive and significant effect on employee job satisfaction and performance. Job stress had a significant negative effect on employee job satisfaction and performance. In addition, job satisfaction was able to partially mediate the relationship between organizational support and job stress on the resulting performance. The theoretical implications of this study contribute to equity theory and social exchange theory, which show that a reciprocal relationship between organizations and employees based on fair support will increase employee motivation and performance. Conversely, high job stress can decrease satisfaction and performance, due to an imbalance in the relationship.

KEYWORDS: Employee performance, job satisfaction, organizational support, work stress

I. INTRODUCTION

Human resources play an important role in organizations to achieve competitive goals of the organization through the performance of its employees (Hassan et al., 2020). Performance can be identified as a person's ability to perform responsibilities related to his/her job (Karaalioglu & Karabulut, 2019). Performance is also usually evaluated from the results of employee behavior for how perfectly an employee has performed or completed his/her tasks (Hassan et al., 2020). One of the plans that is thought to help improve performance is organizational support, minimizing work stress levels, and increasing job satisfaction (Yang et al., 2021).

Based on Kasmir's opinion (2016: 189) there are several factors that influence performance, namely ability, work design, work motivation, work environment and others. The work environment and motivation in this study are discussed as one unit, namely organizational support, which is a factor that plays an important role in determining individual performance. According to To & Huang (2022), organizational support based on *equity theory* also found that fairness in the workplace affects organizational support and is closely related to improving its performance. Organizational support is the employee's perception of the welfare provided by the organization in the form of friendly policies, flexible working hours or supportive superiors (Rubaca & Khan, 2021). Someone who is treated with respect, and the company is sensitive to their needs, then employees will feel the support of the organization so that they make an active contribution to continue trying to meet the goals of an organization (Pemecutan et al., 2016). This is in accordance with what was expressed by Karaalioglu & Karabulut (2019), Chen *et al* (2020), Chaidir *et al* (2023), Arifin & Darmawan (2021), and Eisenberger *et al* (2022) who obtained the results of organizational support having a significant positive effect on employee performance. Other studies conducted by Fitriani et al (2022) and Fathoni & Pujianto (2024) found that organizational support had a significant negative impact on individual employee performance. Meanwhile, research by Yulivianto (2019) and Tombokan *et al* (2019) found that organizational support had a positive but insignificant effect on employee performance.

The perception of organizational support can also be used as a form of fair exchange between the organization and employees which can ultimately build a good relationship between the organization and employees (Arifin & Darmawan, 2021). A good relationship will lead to job satisfaction, as someone sides with their work, actively participates in it, and considers their productivity important for self-esteem. High organizational support for employees increases employee satisfaction levels (Siswanti & Pratiwi, 2020). Several studies have also shown that job satisfaction is influenced by organizational support. The results of research by Cho

& Kim (2019), Maan *et al* (2020), Savitri & Komalasari (2021), Rubaca & Khan (2021), and Irfan & Hakim (2022) state that organizational support has a positive and significant effect on job satisfaction. Research by Thawil & Anwar (2021) concluded that one dimension of organizational support, namely interpersonal justice, has a significant negative effect on job satisfaction. Another opinion from Kurniawan & Farisca (2021) has a negative but insignificant effect on job satisfaction and Septiani & Wijono (2022) found that organizational support has a positive but insignificant effect on improving performance.

In addition to organizational support, which is an important factor in achieving maximum performance is work stress. Work stress has become one of the main strategies to help employees dramatically reduce stress levels and regain control of their work-life balance. Thomas & Kamran's (2021) research explains that when employees witness favoritism, it will cause stress. Based on *social exchange theory*, it is also explained that humans will try to adapt to the conditions around them so that they are viewed well by others. Employees who will develop the quality of relationships through who and how employees interact, as well as how employees' work experiences are (Fauzief & Yanuar, 2021). Work stress can cause negative attitudes and behaviors in individuals, which have a negative impact on job satisfaction due to the negative relationship between work stress and job satisfaction (Wu *et al.*, 2021). This is in accordance with the results of research conducted by Afzal *et al* (2019), Sari *et al* (2021), Iskanto (2021), Yang *et al* (2021), and Mardikaningsih & Sinambela (2022) which found that work stress had a negative and significant effect on employee performance. Other studies such as Ekhsan & Septian (2021) and Kusuma *et al* (2023) concluded that work stress had a significant positive effect on employee performance. Different conclusions from the research of Maulana (2019) and Hassan *et al* (2020) concluded that there was no significant negative relationship between work stress and performance.

Job stress can also cause negative attitudes and behaviors of individuals, which have a negative impact on job satisfaction due to the negative relationship between job stress and job satisfaction (Wu *et al.*, 2021). When individuals experience anxiety that comes from job stress, they are more likely to be dissatisfied (An *et al.*, 2020). Research by Bhastary (2020), Baker & Alshehri (2020), Wu *et al.* (2021), Viegas & Henriques (2021), and Mardikaningsih & Sinambela (2022) states that job stress has a negative and significant effect on job satisfaction. Other studies such as Rivaldo *et al.* (2021) and Astuti *et al.* (2022) concluded that job stress has a significant positive effect on job satisfaction. In contrast, research by Tupamahu *et al.* (2022) and Adinata & Turangan (2023) concluded that there was no significant negative relationship between job stress and job satisfaction.

Each person's level of satisfaction is different and what happens if several factors are met, namely individual needs and their relationship to the level of employee likes and dislikes (Carvalho *et al.*, 2020). Employees who enjoy their work will make more efforts to achieve greater task performance (Karaalioğlu & Karabulut, 2019). This is in accordance with the results of research conducted by An *et al.* (2020), Roberts & David (2020), Carvalho *et al.* (2020), Yang *et al.* (2021), and Marbun & Jufrizen (2022) which state that job satisfaction has a positive and significant effect on employee performance. Research by Fitri & Endratno (2021) in their research concluded that job satisfaction has a significant negative effect on performance. Another study by Nurhandayani (2022) obtained the results of no significant positive effect between employee satisfaction and performance.

Along with the development of the world today, the tourism sector is also experiencing increasing competition, especially in the hotel industry. The hotel industry in Indonesia is one of the sectors that is growing rapidly and is the backbone of national tourism. In this industry, HR is said to be the face of the company that interacts directly with guests (Savitri & Novita, 2022). The friendly, professional, and caring attitude of employees determines the guest experience. HR is not only a resource, but a strategic asset that determines overall business performance. The development of the hospitality industry in Bali is now experiencing positive growth after the Covid-19 pandemic, opening up job opportunities in the tourism sector and it can be seen that Bali is the province with the most hotels in Indonesia.

Based on information from the Central Statistics Agency of Bali Province, it is known that in 2023 compared to 2021 there has been an increase in the number of one-star to five-star hotels. The district with the highest number of hotels is Badung Regency. This growth will certainly increase competition in the tourism industry and encourage each business to show its respective advantages. In order to support and be ready to enter the world of work in the tourism industry, reliable and competent human resources are needed in their fields (kemenparekraf.go.id, 2023). Until February 2024, the absorption of workers into hotels and restaurants increased by 59,790 people when compared to the absorption of workers in the same period in 2023, this increase is the second largest increase with a percentage increase of 23.85 percent. Viewed based on the quality of human resources, based on BPS data, the quality of human resources is still low so it is important to pay attention to human resources in order to obtain maximum performance results.

Internal problems in the hotel industry are also very crucial, this can be seen from cases related to inadequate facilities and infrastructure that are still often found in hotels in Bali and cases of employee welfare being neglected due to unpaid salaries. This is an indication that there are still problems related to organizational support which is suspected of being the cause of less than optimal performance. In addition, work stress is still an important topic that has currently received focus and attention because of the negative impacts on individuals, organizations, and society. Based on information from Kata Data, it is known that lack of appreciation due to not being recognized is the main reason employees are unhappy at work which causes stress (KataData, 2024). Based on the description, the researcher feels the need to conduct research on "The Role of Job Satisfaction in Mediating Organizational Support and Job Stress on Employee Performance at 3-Star Hotels in Badung, Bali"

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

Equity theory

Equity theory or justice theory is a motivational theory that explains that employee motivation in the workplace is largely driven by a sense of justice. This theory was put forward by Stacy Adams in 1963. Based on this theory, employees will make mental notes about the input and output of their work, then compare the ratio of employee input and output with others. Everyone will certainly compare their input and output with others and may feel dissatisfied (Ahmadpour et al., 2022). To & Huang's (2022) research discusses organizational support based on equity theory, finding that fairness in the workplace affects organizational support and is closely related to increasing job satisfaction. In addition, Thomas & Kamran's (2021) research explains that in equity theory, distributive justice is when employees compare the tasks performed and the rewards received to check for fairness and if employees consider it fair, employees will feel satisfied. If an employee witnesses favoritism, then distributive justice becomes a stressor.

Employee performance

According to Sutrisno (2016:172) performance is the result of employee work seen from the aspects of quality, quantity, working time, and cooperation to achieve the goals set by the organization. Employee performance is the result of work in terms of quality and quantity achieved by a person. Performance is a measurement of work in a program that realizes targets in the form of *output* which is the result of an evaluation considered by managers to make a decision (Marbun and Jufrizen, 2022).

Job satisfaction

According to Hasibuan (2017:202) job satisfaction is an emotional attitude that is pleasant and loves one's job. This attitude is reflected by work morale, discipline, and work performance. Job satisfaction is enjoyed in work, outside work, and a combination of inside and outside work. Job satisfaction will create a pleasant feeling that will motivate employees to complete their work (Bhastary, 2020). Job satisfaction has been described as a satisfying and affirmative sentimental condition that is the result of employees' favorable appreciation of their work experience. The difference between what is desired and what is obtained represents job satisfaction (Karaalioglu & Karabulut, 2019).

Organizational Support

According to Kaswan (2017: 224) organizational support means that organizational support given to employees makes employees feel more appreciated and more committed to their work. Perceived organizational support is the perception of how an employee is treated by the organization, which influences the perception of how the organization feels about employee contributions and well-being (Arifin & Darmawan, 2021).

Job Stress

According to Fahmi (2016:214) work stress is a condition that presses a person's soul beyond his/her ability, so that if it is left untreated, it will have an impact on his/her health. Work stress appears in the form of unstable emotions, feeling restless, liking to be alone, difficulty sleeping, smoking excessively, not being able to relax, being anxious, tense, nervous, having high blood pressure, and experiencing digestive disorders (An et al., 2021). In such institutions, workers are required to face unpleasant practices that allow workers to try hard to do their jobs in difficult situations.

III. RESEARCH METHODS

This study uses a quantitative approach based on the philosophy of positivism which is used to research a certain population or sample, data collection using research instruments, quantitative data analysis, with the aim of testing the established hypothesis. The design used in this study is to design all activities that will be used in conducting related research starting from identifying problems in 3-star hotels in Badung Bali, determining the hypotheses studied by the study, analyzing data obtained from respondents and reporting conclusions and suggestions for improving future writing . The process of finding data uses a survey method with an instrument in the form of a questionnaire. The *Likert scale* is used as a measuring tool to measure the variables in this study. Determination of the number of samples using 5 times the number of indicators taken using *non-probability sampling with purposive sampling* techniques . Data analysis in this study uses SEM (*Structural Equation Modeling*) analysis based on PLS (*Partial Least Square*).

IV. RESULTS

Hypothesis testing will be conducted using SEM based on PLS (*Partial Least Squares*). This method is suitable for analyzing complex relationships between variables without strict assumptions about data distribution. This analysis includes an external model assessed through *convergent validity*, *discriminant validity*, and *composite reliability* and *cronbach alpha* . The model in *R-Square* (R^2), *Q-Square Predictive Relevance* (Q2), *Goodness of Fit* (GoF). Furthermore, hypothesis testing and mediation role testing are carried out.

Path Analysis and Hypothesis Testing

The path coefficient value (*t-value*) is used to test the significance of a construct or latent variable through the estimation of the path coefficient value (*t-value*) obtained by the *bootstrapping procedure* with a value considered significant if the p value <0.05 . The test results are presented in Table 1 .

Table 1. Path Statistical Analysis

	Original Sample (O)	Standard Deviation (STDEV)	T Deviation (O/STDEV)	P Values Statistics
Support -> Employee Performance	0.240	0.087	2,763	0.006
Organizational Support -> Job Satisfaction	0.324	0.090	3,604	0,000
Job Stress -> Employee Performance	-0.230	0.055	4,197	0,000
Job Stress -> Job Satisfaction	-0.215	0.064	3,365	0.001
Job Satisfaction -> Employee Performance	0.523	0.089	5,871	0,000

Source: Processed data (2025)

The calculation results in Table 1 can be explained as follows.

- Organizational support has a positive influence on performance with a coefficient of 0.240 and the relationship is significant at the level of $0.006 < 0.05$.
- Organizational support has a positive effect on job satisfaction with a coefficient of 0.324 and the relationship is significant at the level of $0.000 < 0.05$.
- Work stress has a negative influence on performance with a coefficient of -0.215 and the relationship is significant at the level of $0.001 < 0.05$.
- Job stress has a negative influence on job satisfaction with a coefficient of -0.230 and the relationship is significant at the level of $0.000 < 0.05$.
- Job satisfaction has a positive influence on performance with a coefficient of 0.523 and the relationship is significant at the level of $0.000 < 0.05$.

Table 2. Testing the Role of Mediating

	Original Sample (O)	Standard Deviation (STDEV)	T	Statistics (O/STDEV)	P Values
Organizational Support -> Job Satisfaction -> Employee Performance	0.170	0.058	2,916		0.004
Job Stress -> Job Satisfaction -> Employee Performance	-0.112	0.042	2,689		0.007

Source: Processed data (2025)

- f. The direct influence of organizational support on employee performance has a coefficient value of 0.240 and is significant, in addition, the indirect relationship through mediation has a coefficient value of 0.170 with a significant influence so that it can be concluded that job satisfaction is able to partially mediate the influence of organizational support on employee performance.
- g. The direct effect of work stress on employee performance has a coefficient value of 0.215 and is significant, in addition, the indirect relationship through mediation has a coefficient value of 0.112 with a significant effect so that it can be concluded that job satisfaction is able to partially mediate the effect of work stress on employee performance.

V. DISCUSSION

The Influence of Organizational Support on Employee Performance

Based on the results of the analysis of the influence of organizational support on employee performance, it shows that organizational support has a positive and significant effect on employee performance. This indicates that the better the organizational support provided by management at star hotels in Badung Bali, the better the employee performance produced. Based on the highest *outer loading value*, it is reflected in the ease of obtaining leave rights, so that this ease becomes a determining factor for organizational support that can improve employee performance.

Organizational support provided by hotel management to employees is reflected in employee perceptions of the organization's attention and commitment to their welfare. Based on respondents' answers, it is known that employee perceptions of organizational support are in the good category. The highest is the existence of equality in the work environment. Employees who feel supported by the organization believe that in every situation in work or personal life where the organization is ready to help employees will provide encouragement to employees to be willing to work optimally. This support not only makes employees feel respected, cared for, and recognized, but also creates a sense of equality in the work environment.

On the other hand, there are still two indicators that have values below average, namely the organization's concern for employee welfare and ease in obtaining leave rights have values below average. This shows that employees need to feel fair and equal treatment in order to feel more motivated to work optimally, improve teamwork, and build positive reciprocal relationships with coworkers and management.

This ultimately contributes to improving overall employee performance (Marbun & Jufrizen, 2022). These results are in accordance with the conclusions expressed in the research of Karaalioglu & Karabulut (2019) who studied the performance of 700 energy sector employees in Istanbul, Chen *et al* (2020) who studied university lecturers in Taiwan, Arifin & Darmawan (2021) at a company in Mojokerto City, Eisenberger *et al* (2022) who conducted a study on empirical findings over the past three decades in the United States, and Chaidir *et al* (2023) PT. Pertamina Region III Depot Cilegon obtained the results of organizational support having a significant positive effect on employee performance.

The Influence of Organizational Support on Job Satisfaction

Based on the results of the analysis of the influence of organizational support on job satisfaction, it shows that organizational support has a positive and significant effect on employee job satisfaction. This indicates that the better the organizational support at 3-star hotels in Badung Bali, the higher the employee satisfaction. Based on the highest *outer loading value*, it is reflected in the ease of obtaining leave rights, so that this ease becomes a determining factor in organizational support that can increase employee satisfaction.

The perception of organizational support can be used as a form of fair exchange between the organization and employees which can ultimately build a good relationship between the organization and employees. Based on the respondents' answers, it is known that employee perceptions of organizational support are in the good category. The highest is the existence of equality in the work environment. Meanwhile, the organization's concern for employee welfare and ease in obtaining leave rights have values below average. Based on the characteristics of the respondents, it can be seen that most employees have a work period of 1-5 years, which indicates employee satisfaction with organizational support so that they are willing to stay in the organization. Organizational support as measured by fairness, support from superiors and organizational awards and working conditions has been managed well so that it contributes to employee job satisfaction.

These results are in accordance with the conclusions expressed in the research of Cho & Kim (2019) who conducted research on nurses in Korea, Maan *et al* (2020) who studied 936 employees working in various manufacturing fields, Savitri & Komalasari (2021) who also studied the hotel sector, namely employees of The Santai Umalas-Bali, Rubaca & Khan (2021) used 45 Pakistani firefighters as respondents, and Irfan & Hakim (2022) who studied private hospitals in Sidoarjo City stated that organizational support has a positive and significant effect on job satisfaction.

The Impact of Work Stress on Employee Performance

Based on the results of the analysis of the influence of work stress on employee performance, it shows that work stress has a negative and significant effect on employee performance. This indicates that the higher the work stress of star hotel employees in Badung Bali, the lower the employee performance will be. Based on the highest *outer loading value*, it is reflected by stress due to an unsupportive work system, which causes stress to increase and ultimately can reduce employee performance.

Job stress is a feeling of pressure experienced by employees in dealing with work. Based on respondents' answers, employee assessments of job stress are in the sufficient category, meaning that employee stress levels do not burden individuals in the company too much. However, the highest level of stress is stress due to not being able to adapt easily to the environment. This means that most employees still have poor socializing skills. When viewed based on the characteristics of respondents, most employees are aged 19-25 years where this age still requires a lot of guidance in interacting. In addition, there are still many employees who have a work period of less than one year, which is one of the factors of high job stress that can cause low performance.

Stress that is not managed properly and reaches excessive levels will have a very detrimental impact on performance. High stress can cause fatigue, confusion, and decreased concentration, making it difficult for employees to focus on their tasks and increasing the likelihood of errors. This of course is detrimental to employee performance and can affect productivity and the overall work atmosphere. High levels of work stress can have a negative impact on employee productivity, mental and physical health, and overall organizational performance, resulting in decreased performance.

These results are in accordance with the conclusions expressed in the research of Afzal *et al.* (2019) who studied employees in Pakistan, Sari *et al.* (2021) who studied employees working in the manufacturing industry in Indonesia, Iskanto (2021) who studied employees in the administration and sales divisions in Pekanbaru, Yang *et al.* (2021) studied the High-Tech and Traditional Industries in Taiwan, and Mardikaningsih & Sinambela (2022) who studied a company in Indonesia found that work stress had a negative and significant effect on performance.

The Influence of Job Stress on Job Satisfaction

Based on the results of the analysis of the influence of work stress on job satisfaction, it shows that work stress has a negative and significant effect on employee job satisfaction. This indicates that the higher the employee stress in star hotels in Badung Bali, the lower the employee satisfaction will be. Based on the highest *outer loading value*, it is reflected by stress due to an unsupportive work system, which causes stress to increase and ultimately can reduce employee job satisfaction.

Stress is something very natural that affects emotions and moods. Stress is the most common problem faced by every individual in completing work. Based on the respondents' answers, the level of employee stress is in the sufficient category, but the highest work stress assessed by employees of 3-star hotels in Badung Bali is stress due to not being able to adapt easily to the environment. This is the cause of low employee job satisfaction because the work environment is one of the important factors that shape employee perceptions of their workplace.

Job stress is an organizational problem that affects employee job satisfaction so that employees who experience various symptoms of stress can worsen employee moods. This causes employees to experience more negative emotions so that job satisfaction will decrease. Negative emotions caused by stress that is felt ultimately reduce employee job satisfaction.

These results are in accordance with the conclusions expressed in the research of Bhastary (2020) who studied all employees of PT. PLN (Persero) UIP3BS UPT Medan, Baker & Alshehri (2020) who studied Saudi Arabian Nurses, Wu *et al* (2021) who studied 1464 bank employees in China, Viegas & Henriques (2021) who studied police officers at the Goa Police Department, and Mardikaningsih & Sinambela (2022) who tested at a company in Indonesia stated that work stress has a negative and significant effect on job satisfaction.

The Influence of Job Satisfaction on Employee Performance

Based on the results of the analysis of the influence of job satisfaction on employee performance, it shows that job satisfaction has a positive and significant effect on employee performance. This indicates that high employee satisfaction will improve performance. Likewise, low job satisfaction will decrease performance in 3-star hotel employees in Badung Bali. Based on the highest outer loading value, it is reflected in the opportunity to obtain the position given, so that this convenience becomes a determining factor in increasing job satisfaction which causes better performance.

Job satisfaction is an attitude, behavior, and perspective of an employee in carrying out work. Job satisfaction is personal so that job satisfaction between employees will be different where job satisfaction will affect the work done by employees (Saputra & Laksmi, 2024). In this study, employee job satisfaction is in the good category, meaning that most employees have satisfaction in themselves by working at a 3-star hotel in Badung Bali. In addition, it can be seen that the supervision of the leader gets the highest value which is able to encourage employees to work better on the other hand, the opportunity to obtain the position given and the relationship that occurs with coworkers is one indication of lack of satisfaction because the value obtained is below average.

Job satisfaction serves as a control tool that causes employees to perform better, which will result in higher economic rewards. If the reward is considered appropriate and fair, greater satisfaction will arise because employees feel that they receive rewards according to their achievements, so high job satisfaction will help them improve the performance produced (Jayawarsa *et al.*, 2024).

These results are in accordance with the conclusions expressed by An *et al.* (2020) who studied merchant sailors at Yangshan Port, Shanghai, China, Roberts & David (2020) who studied workers in the United States, Carvalho *et al.* (2020) who studied employees of Cooperativa Café Timor in Timor Leste, Yang *et al.* (2021) who conducted comparative research on the High-Tech industry and Traditional Industry in Taiwan, and Marbun & Jufrizen (2022) who studied employees of the Food Security and Livestock Service Office of North Sumatra Province stated that job satisfaction has a positive and significant effect on employee performance.

The Mediating Role of Job Satisfaction in the Influence of Organizational Support on Employee Performance

Based on the results of testing the direct influence of organizational support on employee performance has a positive and significant influence, in addition to the indirect relationship through mediation of job satisfaction has a significant influence. These results indicate that job satisfaction is able to partially mediate the influence of organizational support on employee performance. Perceived organizational support is related to positive work performance and attitudes such as increased performance and decreased dissatisfaction with something at work. Furthermore, job satisfaction is a well-identified mediator and is an antecedent of performance.

High levels of job satisfaction result in increased work results. In this study, respondents' answers regarding organizational support, job satisfaction and performance are in the good category, which means that support factors can increase satisfaction and performance. Job satisfaction in this study has been proven to be an important factor that causes the high influence of organizational

support on the resulting performance. An organization that provides support to its employees will make employees happy and in the end employees will give back in the form of the best performance for the organization.

This is in accordance with research by Karaalioglu & Karabulut (2019) who studied the performance of 700 energy sector employees in Istanbul, Siswanti & Pratiwi (2020), Marbun & Jufrizen (2022) who studied employees of the North Sumatra Provincial Food Security and Livestock Service Office, and Siregar & Pasaribu (2022) who studied employees of PT. Aman Bahari Kuala Tanjung stated that there is a significant relationship between organizational support and employee performance through satisfaction.

The Mediating Role of Job Satisfaction in the Influence of Job Stress on Employee Performance

The direct effect of work stress on employee performance obtained significant negative results, in addition to the indirect relationship through mediation of job satisfaction also had a significant effect. These results indicate that job satisfaction is able to partially mediate the effect of work stress on employee performance. This means that the seventh hypothesis in the study is accepted.

Stress causes reduced job satisfaction and ultimately hinders workers from carrying out their duties effectively. The level of a person's response to external stimuli and forces that cause stress, ignoring the influence of interactions of other factors such as the characteristics of the individual himself with the characteristics and conditions of the work environment which are the basis for determining the amount of pressure felt by a person. In this study, the level of stress is in the sufficient category while satisfaction and performance based on respondents' answers are in the good category. This means that the imbalance in the workplace due to the tension that occurs in it causes a person to be unable to fulfill the role he plays in the workplace, ultimately work stress will reduce the level of employee satisfaction so that the resulting performance will decrease.

This research is in accordance with the conclusions expressed in the research of Maulana (2019) who studied employees of PT. Tema (Trijaya Excel Madura), Filliantoni et al. (2019) who studied employees of Indomobil Nissan-Datsun Solobaru, Nisar & Rasheed (2020) who studied police working in AJ&K Pakistan, Amanda et al. (2022) who studied Class I Non TPI Karawang Immigration Employees, and Mardikaningsih & Sinambela (2022) who studied a company in Indonesia which revealed that job satisfaction can mediate the effect of work stress on employee performance.

VI. CONCLUSION

1. Organizational support has a positive and significant effect on the performance of 3-star hotel employees in Badung Bali. Organizational support as a form of fair exchange between the organization and employees can help employees to produce maximum performance. This means that better organizational support will improve performance.
2. Organizational support has a positive and significant effect on employee job satisfaction at 3-star hotels in Badung Bali. Organizational support as a form of management attention to employees that provides satisfaction to the employees themselves, so that better organizational support will increase employee job satisfaction.
3. Job stress has a negative and significant effect on the performance of 3-star hotel employees in Badung Bali. Job stress is the cause of employee fatigue so that higher stress levels will decrease performance.
4. Job stress has a negative and significant effect on job satisfaction of 3-star hotel employees in Badung Bali. Stress causes changes in employee mood or emotions so that higher stress will decrease job satisfaction.
5. Job satisfaction has a positive and significant effect on the performance of 3-star hotel employees in Badung Bali. Job satisfaction is an employee's view of their work that drives them to act, so that higher job satisfaction will improve performance.
6. Job satisfaction is able to partially mediate the influence of organizational support on employee performance at 3-star hotels in Badung Bali. In this study, part of the influence of organizational support on employee performance can be explained by job satisfaction. Employees' feelings of happiness can increase organizational support for employee performance. The better the organizational support given to employees, the more satisfaction they will provide and ultimately improve performance.
7. Job satisfaction is able to partially mediate the influence of work stress on employee performance at 3-star hotels in Badung Bali. In this study, part of the influence of work stress on employee performance can be explained by job satisfaction. Employees' feelings of happiness can be an important factor that reduces the influence of work stress on employee performance. The higher the employee stress, the lower the employee's satisfaction and ultimately the lower the performance.

VII. SUGGESTION

Based on the research results, then The suggestions given to the management of 3-star hotels in Badung Regency, Bali include several important aspects in terms of organizational support, where management is expected to pay more attention to employee welfare by providing benefit programs such as health insurance or transportation facilities. To overcome work stress, stress management and emotional control training are needed, as well as creating a supportive work environment through open communication and an internal community that strengthens togetherness. Meanwhile, job satisfaction can be increased by providing a clear career path and *soft skill development programs* such as *team building* to improve teamwork. In addition, in terms of performance, management is expected to involve employees more in determining targets and providing training that focuses on *problem-solving*, time management, and technical skills.

Employees are expected to be more open in conveying their needs to management, utilizing existing welfare facilities, and developing skills in dealing with work stress by understanding procedures and discussing with coworkers. Employees are also expected to be more proactive in career development by asking for feedback *and* improving relationships with coworkers through social activities. In addition, employees need to hone their *problem-solving skills* through training and pay more attention to work details to reduce errors.

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